

The Psalm Project

Discovering the Spiritual World through the Psalms

Psalm 85

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The Goal of this project:

This research project will examine the 150 psalms for the spiritual awareness each Psalm offers. Each Psalm will be examined by its language and the commentary of the Sages. The spiritual awareness analysis will be done in alignment with Ari's definition of the Tree of life, the Book of Creation, and the Zohar. Each verse of the Psalm will be rewritten using the intent of the language and spiritual commentary to convey its spiritual lesson.

The Main Resources:

The Zohar

The Book of Creation

Ari's writing on the Tree of Life and the Ten Sefirot

The Theological Wordbook of the Old Testament

Samson Hirsch's commentary on the Psalms

Tehillim – Psalms – A new translation with a commentary anthologized from the Talmudic and rabbinic sources

Accordance Bible Software

Psalm 85

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>Psa. 85:0 For the choir director. A Psalm of the sons of Korah.</p>	<p style="text-align: right;">Psa. 85:1</p> <p style="text-align: center;">לְמִנְצֵחַ אֲלֹהֵי-קָרַח</p>
<p>Psa. 85:1 O LORD, You showed ^afavor to Your land; You ^{1b}restored the captivity of Jacob. ²You ^aforgave the iniquity of Your people; You ^bcovered all their sin. ¹Selah. ³You ^awithdrew all Your fury; You ^bturned away from Your burning anger.</p>	<p>מִזְמוֹר : ² רָצִיתָ יְהוָה אֶרְצֶךָ שְׁבֹתָ שְׁבוֹת [שְׁבִית] יַעֲקֹב : ³ גָּשַׁתָּ עֵינֶיךָ עֲמַתְךָ כָּסִיתָ כָּל-חַטָּאתָם סֵלָה : ⁴ אָסַפְתָּ כָּל-עֲבֹרֹתֶיךָ הַשִּׁיבוֹתָ מִחֲרוֹן אַפֶּיךָ : ⁵ שׁוּבוּנוּ אֱלֹהֵי יִשְׂרָאֵל וְהִפֵּר כַּעֲסֶךָ עִמָּנוּ : ⁶ הִלְעֹלָם תִּיאַנְּךָ-בָּנוּ תִמְשָׁךְ אַפֶּיךָ לְדָר וָדָר : ⁷ הֲלֹא-אַתָּה תָּשׁוּב תִּתִּיבֵנוּ וְעֲמַתְךָ יִשְׁמְחוּ-בָּךְ : ⁸ תִּרְאֵנוּ יְהוָה חֲסִדֶיךָ וְיִשְׁעֶיךָ תִּתֵּן-לָנוּ : ⁹ אֲשַׁמְּעָה מִה- יִדְבַר הָאֵל אִיהוָה כִּי אִידְבֹּר שְׁלוֹם אֶל-עַמּוֹ וְאֶל-חֲסִידָיו וְאֶל- יִשְׂרָאֵל לְכִסְלָה : ¹⁰ אֵךְ אֶךְ אֶךְ רָוֹב לִירְאָיו יִשְׁעוּ לְשֹׁכֵן כְּבוֹד בְּאֶרְצָנוּ : ¹¹ חֲסִד-וְאֱמֶת נִפְגְּשׁוּ צֶדֶק וְשְׁלוֹם נִשְׁקִי : ¹² אֱמֶת מֵאֲרֶץ תִּצְמַח וְצֶדֶק מִשָּׁמַיִם נִשְׁקֶף : ¹³ גַּם- יְהוָה יִתֵּן תִּטּוֹב וְאֶרְצָנוּ תִּתֵּן יְבוּלָה : ¹⁴ צֶדֶק לְפָנָיו יִהְיֶה וְיִשָּׂם לְדָרְךָ פְּעָמָיו :</p>
<p>Psa. 85:4 ^aRestore us, O God of our salvation, And ^bcause Your indignation toward us to cease. ⁵Will ^aYou be angry with us forever? Will You prolong Your anger to ¹all generations? ⁶Will You not Yourself ^{1a}revive us again, That Your people may ^brejoice in You? ⁷Show us Your lovingkindness, O LORD, And ^agrant us Your salvation.</p>	
<p>Psa. 85:8 ¹I will hear what God the LORD will say; For He will ^aspeak peace to His people, ²to His godly ones;</p>	

But let them not ^bturn back to
³folly.

⁹ Surely ^aHis salvation is near to
those who ¹fear Him,

That ^bglory may dwell in our land.

¹⁰ ^aLovingkindness and ¹truth have
met together;

^bRighteousness and peace have
kissed each other.

¹¹ ¹Truth ^asprings from the earth,
And righteousness looks down
from heaven.

¹² Indeed, ^athe LORD will give what
is good,

And our ^bland will yield its
produce.

¹³ ^aRighteousness will go before Him
And will make His footsteps into a
way.

References

Psalm 85:1

¹Or *restore the fortunes*

^aPs 77:7; 106:4

^bEzra 1:11; Ps 14:7; 126:1; Jer 30:18; Ezek 39:25; Hos 6:11; Joel 3:1

Psalm 85:2

¹*Selah* may mean: *Pause, Crescendo* or *Musical interlude*

^aNum 14:19; 1 Kin 8:34; Ps 78:38; 103:3; Jer 31:34

^bPs 32:1

Psalm 85:3

^aPs 78:38; 106:23

^bEx 32:12; Deut 13:17; Ps 106:23; Jon 3:9

Psalm 85:4

^aPs 80:3, 7

^bDan 9:16

Psalm 85:5

¹Lit *generation and generation*

^aPs 74:1; 79:5; 80:4

Psalm 85:6

¹Or *bring to life*

^aPs 71:20; 80:18

^bPs 33:1; 90:14; 149:2

Psalm 85:7

^aPs 106:4

Psalm 85:8

¹Or *Let me hear*

²Lit *even to*

³Or *stupidity*

^aPs 29:11; Hag 2:9; Zech 9:10

^bPs 78:57; 2 Pet 2:21

Psalm 85:9

¹Or *reverence*

^aPs 34:18; Is 46:13

^bPs 84:11; Hag 2:7; Zech 2:5; John 1:14

Psalm 85:10

¹Or *faithfulness*

^aPs 25:10; 89:14; Prov 3:3

^bPs 72:3; Is 32:17

Psalm 85:11

¹Or *Faithfulness*

^aIs 45:8

Psalm 85:12

^aPs 84:11; James 1:17

^bLev 26:4; Ps 67:6; Ezek 34:27; Zech 8:12

Psalm 85:13

^aPs 89:14

Targum

Psa. 85:1 For praise; composed by the sons of Korah; a psalm. ² You delighted, O LORD, in your land; you brought back the captivity of the house of Jacob. ³ You forgave the sins of your people; you covered all their faults forever. ⁴ You withdrew all your anger; you turned from the harshness of your anger. ⁵ Turn to us, O God our redemption; and revoke your anger against us. ⁶ Can it be that you will act harshly against us forever? Will you prolong out your harshness for all generations? ⁷ Will you not again revive us? And your people will rejoice in your word. ⁸ Show us, O LORD, your goodness; and may your redemption be given to us. ⁹ I will hear what God, the LORD, will say; for he will speak peace to his people and to his pious ones, and they will not return to heathenism. ¹⁰ Truly, his redemption is near to those who fear him, to make glory abide in our land. ¹¹ Favor and truth meet, righteousness and peace have joined together. ¹² Truth grew up from the land; and righteousness looked out from heaven. ¹³ Also the LORD will give what is good; and our land will give its produce. ¹⁴ Righteousness will walk before him; and he set his steps on a good path.

Spiritual Awareness

Introduction

This Psalm's subject is Israel's return from the Babylonian Exile to build the Second Temple. Unfortunately, the Second Temple was destroyed by the Romans in 70 CE. Israel has yearned for a permanent redemption in which the LORD will be wholly reconciled to His land. The fertility of the land was the most accurate measurement of the LORD's favorable attitude toward Israel. The LORD wants the earth to flourish, so His Chosen people will have a healthy and prosperous life.

Superscript

To the Sefirah Netzach who grants victory, by the sons of Korach, a psalm.

Verse two

**You have forgiven the iniquity of Your people and covered up all their sins.
Meditate on this verse.**

Notes

The people in Exile pleaded to the LORD to allow them to return to their homeland. The land of Israel was promised to the Chosen People through the LORD's covenant with Abraham. While in Babylon, the people realized that their sins caused the LORD to respond harshly. The LORD sent prophets and messengers to the leaders of Judah. The message about their sins was clearly given. Yet the people continued to sin. The LORD had no choice but to bring the Babylonians to Judah to Exile the people. The

worship of Tammuz and other gods in the Temple forced the Shekinah to leave the Temple. When this happened the Babylonians were able to destroy the Temple without any resistance. The Temple which was dedicated to the LORD was tainted with pagan worship. It was a sad day when the destruction of the Temple and Jerusalem occurred.

Appendix

Mystical Methodology to Prayer

All prayers result in spiritual energy which rises through the conduits that connect Sefirot realms. The "answer" to prayers is the transformation of spiritual energy from its original frequency to an appropriate frequency which will give the necessary results.

MHK V5 1/17/2016

Chambers of Aba and Ima of Briyah

Keter: prayers of thanksgiving come

